

***FESTUCA FLORIBUNDA*, A NEW COMBINATION FOR *DIELSIOCHLOA*
(POACEAE: POOIDEAE: POEAE: LOLIODINAE: LOLIINAE)**

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ABSTRACT

Based on morphological and molecular evidence, *Trisetum floribundum* [syn. *Dielsiochloa floribunda* (Pilg.) Pilg.] is transferred to *Festuca* as ***Festuca floribunda*** (Pilg.) P.M. Peterson, Soreng & Romasch., **comb. nov.** Specimens examined (Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Peru) are included.

Pilger (1906) described *Trisetum floribundum* based on two syntypes collected by A. Weberbauer [nos. 1028 & 2811] from Peru. Hitchcock (1927) effectively chose *Weberbauer 1028* as a lectotype in his treatment of the Grasses of Ecuador, Peru, and Bolivia but did not cite a herbarium. Thirty-seven years later Pilger (1943) erected the new genus *Dielsiochloa* Pilg., with a single species [*D. floribunda*] and three varieties. He also stated that *Weberbauer 1028* was “Typus der Art.” Pilger (1943, p. 100) mentioned that *Dielsiochloa* was roughly similar to species in *Bromus* sect. *Stenobromus* Griseb. (= *Bromus* sect. *Genea* Dumort., including *B. sterilis* L. and *B. madritensis* L.; see Soreng et al. 2018), in which the upper florets within a spikelet are sterile with an irregularly disarticulating rachilla, and he concluded that the genus belonged in tribe Aveneae s. l. near *Trisetum*.

Most systematists have followed this phylogenetic assessment of the species (Nicora 1975; Clayton & Renvoize 1986; Nicora & Rúgolo de Agrasar 1987; Tovar 1993; Chiappella 2012). *Dielsiochloa floribunda* is characterized in having 6–10-flowered spikelets (only the lower 2 or 3 fertile, upper sterile and diminished), 1-veined glumes shorter than the spikelet, 5-veined lemmas bearing a single erect awn (5–10 mm long) arising dorsally below a bifid apex (notch 1–3.2 mm deep with aristate, hyaline teeth), glabrous ovaries, and a dorsally compressed caryopses with an adherent pericarp (Clayton et al. 2006).

Currently, the United States National Herbarium is being rearranged in a new classification following Soreng et al. (2017) and we came to *Dielsiochloa*, a taxon we have known was embedded within *Festuca* L. for over 10 years (Quintanar et al. 2007; Döring 2009; Refulio et al. 2012; Saarela et al. unpubl. (sequences in GenBank); Romaschenko et al. unpubl. (sequences in GenBank)). In a molecular DNA study using *trnTL-trnLF* and ITS markers, Minaya (2017) found *D. floribunda* deeply embedded in a derived clade of northern South American festucas and sister to *Festuca cuzcoensis* Stančík & P.M. Peterson, a species known only from the higher elevations (3200–3850 m) of Bolivia and Peru (Stančík & Peterson 2002). We believe the species belongs in *Festuca* and make the new combination below.

FESTUCA FLORIBUNDA (Pilg.) P.M. Peterson, Soreng, & Romasch., **comb. nov.** *Trisetum floribundum* Pilg., Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 37: 505. 1906. *Dielsiochloa floribunda* (Pilg.) Pilg., Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 73: 99. 1943. **LECTOTYPE** (designated by Hitchcock in Contr. U.S. Natl. Herb. 24: 359. 1927): **Peru.** Prov. Sandia: unterhalb Ananea, auf sehr durftig bewachsenem, steinigem Boden, 4800 m, 15 May 1902, A. *Weberbauer 1028* (B, image B100250163!; isolectotypes: S image S-R-6247!, SGO image SGO000000770!).

The species is found in the Cordillera de los Andes of northwestern Argentina, Bolivia, northern Chile, and Peru at 4000–5100 m. It grows on steep, rocky, gravelly slopes, talus slopes, rock outcrops, wet meadows, and lake shores associated with *Festuca*, *Poa*, *Cinnagrostis* (syn. *Calamagrostis* Adans., *Deyeuxia* Clarion ex P. Beauv.), *Anatherostipa*, *Jarava*, *Pappostipa*, *Azorella*, *Lepidophyllum*, *Polylepis*, and *Pycnophyllum*.

Festuca floribunda shares with other members of the genus lemmas with a rounded back, a glabrous callus that is blunt and annulated, and a dorsoventrally compressed rachilla (Watson & Dallwitz 1992; Clayton et al. 2006). *Festuca casapaltensis* Ball, a Peruvian endemic, is morphologically similar to *F. floribunda* in having short tufted culms, lemmas with long slender awns, and glumes longer than the lower floret with attenuate apices (Tovar 1972, 1993).

Specimens examined: **ARGENTINA. Jujuy.** Dpto. Famatina. Sierra de Famatina, *Krapovickas* 6241 (BAA); Dpto. Humahuaca: 150 m below cumbre del Aguilar, *Ruthsatz* 493 (BAA). **BOLIVIA. La Paz.** Prov. Murillo, La Paz, hacia la Cumbre, 10 Jul 2004, *Beck & Beck* 31058 (LPB, US); Prov. Murillo, Nevado Chacaltaya al norte de La Paz, 6 Feb 1989, *Beck* 14695 (LPB, US); Prov. Murillo, Mina Milluni, 15 May 1985, *Beck* 11197 (LPB, US); Prov. Murillo, the dam at Lago Zongo, 17 Apr 1985, *Solomon* 13367 (MO, US); Prov. Murillo, 6.6 km N of the road to Valle del Zongo, on the road to Chacaltaya, 15 Mar 1984, *Solomon* 11784, *Stein & Uehlong* (MO, US). **Potosí.** Prov. Sud Chichas, 20 mi E of Atocha and 1.5 mi above Santa Barbara on the southwest face of Nevada Choroloque, 15 Mar 1993, *Peterson* 12939, *Annable, Soreng, Laegaard & Rojas-Ponce* (LPB, US); Sud Lipez, 2 mi N of San Antonio de Lipez, 20 Mar 1993, *Peterson* 13024, *Soreng & Laegaard* (LPB, US); Sud Lipez, 27 mi SW of San Antonio de Lipez and 22 mi NE of Quentena Chico, 21 Mar 1993, *Peterson* 13053, *Soreng & Laegaard* (LPB, US). **CHILE. Region I.** 26 km E of Zapahuira on top of Cerro Chapiquiña, 18°20'7.1"S, 69°30'3.6"W, 1 Apr 2001, *Peterson* 15721 & *Soreng* (CONC, US); 92 km NE of Huara on road towards Colchane, 19°37'55.3"S, 69°4'11.5"W, 26 Mar 2001, *Peterson* 15636 & *Soreng* (CONC, US); 106 km NE of Huara on road towards Colchane, 19°34'53.2"S, 68°58'1.1"W, 26 Mar 2001, *Peterson* 15653 & *Soreng* (CONC, US). **Region II.** km 45 on road from San Pedro to Paso Jama, 22°55'30"S, 67°45'41"W, 16 Mar 2001, *Peterson* 15526, *Soreng & Judziewicz* (CONC, US). **PERU.** Between Culini and Obrajillo, Wilkes Expedition (US-868484); 21 km E of Pachacofo on road towards Hullanca, 9°52'59.0"S, 77°12'4.5"W, 21 Mar 2004, *Peterson* 17912, *Refulio Rodriguez, Cano, LaTorre & Salinas* (US, USM). **Ancash.** Bolognesi Prov., Paso Chonta, 29 Apr 1956, *Tovar* 2663 (USM, US); Bolognesi Prov., Abra Yanashallas, W of Huallanca and 55 km E of Conococha, 9°51'36.1"S, 77°4'41.6"W, 24 Mar 2004, *Peterson* 17947 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Bolognesi Prov., 5 km NW of Abra Yanashalash on road towards Antimina, 9°50'3.5"S, 77°6'57.6"W, 25 Mar 2004, *Peterson* 17963 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Recuay Prov., Huascarán National Park, Quebrada Quenua Ragra, 10 May 1985, *Smith* 10652, *Valencia & Gonzales* (MO, US); Yungay Prov., Cordillera Negra, Cerro Chonta, at head of Quebrada Teclio, 9°17'50.3"S, 77°48'30.4"W, 14 Mar 2008, *Peterson* 21668, *Soreng, LaTorre & Rojas Fox* (US, USM); Yungay Prov., Cordillera Blanca, on road to pass E of Lago Llanganuco and Yanama, 9°2'39.9"S, 77°35'47.3"W, 16 Mar 2008, *Peterson* 21761, *Soreng, LaTorre & Rojas Fox* (US, USM). **Arequipa.** Nevado de Chachani, 14 Apr 1925, *Pennell* 13313 (US); Arequipa Prov., 11 km NE of Patahuasi on road towards Chivay, 15°57'59.1"S, 71°22'45.9"W, 11 Apr 2004, *Peterson* 18258 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Caylloma Prov., 15 km SE of Callalli on road towards Condorama, 15°28'14"S, 71°22'26.9"W, 12 Apr 2004, *Peterson* 18274 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Caylloma Prov., 10 km SE of Callalli on road towards Condorama, 15°29'26"S, 71°23'5.9"W, 12 Apr 2004, *Peterson* 18261 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Caylloma Prov., Bosque de Rocas, S of Imata, 12 km on road to Pati, 75 air km NE of Arequipa, 15°54'37.4"S, 71°2'38"W, 1 Apr 2007, *Peterson* 20758, *Soreng, Romaschenko & Gonzalez Elizondo* (US, USM); Caylloma Prov., S of Imata, 17 km on road to Pati, 6 km S of Bosque de Rocas, 73 air km NE of Arequipa, 15°57'40"S, 71°2'14.4"W, 1 Apr 2007, *Peterson* 20769, *Soreng, Romaschenko & Gonzalez Elizondo* (US, USM). **Ayacucho.** Cangallo Prov., just S of Abra Apacheta, 84 km W of Ayacucho on road to Pisco, 13°21'28.9"S, 74°43'57.1"W, 22 Mar 2002, *Peterson* 16661 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Cangallo Prov., 0.5 km E of Abra Apacheta on road towards Ayacucho, 13°21'28.8"S, 74°43'57.2"W, 5 Apr 2004, *Peterson* 18165 & *Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Lucanas Prov., 51 km SE of Puquio and 24

km NW of Chavina, 14°52'2.2"S, 73°55'40.2"W, 27 Feb 2002, *Peterson 16313*, *La Torre, Ramirez & Susanibar Cruz* (US, USM); Lucanas Prov., 55 km E of Puquio on road towards Cuzco, 14°38'15.5"S, 73°49'51.3"W, 12 Mar 2002, *Peterson 16464 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Lucanas Prov., 4 km N of Pedregal and 49 km S of Putajasa, 14°24'30.4"S, 74°24'23.5"W, 23 Feb 2002, *Peterson 16197*, *Cano, LaTorre, Ramirez & Susanibar Cruz* (US, USM); Lucanas Prov., 28 km W of Lucanas at jtn of road to Saisa, 14°39'40.1"S, 74°19'8.8"W, 8 Apr 2004, *Peterson 18195 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Parinacochas/Paucar del Sara Sara Prov., S and SE slopes of Nevado Sara Sara, 15°21'16.9"S, 73°28'47.2", 2 Mar 2002, *Peterson 16365*, *La Torre, Ramirez & Susanibar Cruz* (US, USM). **Huancavelica.** Castrovirreyna Prov., Laguna Choclococha, 2 May 1958, *Tovar 2825, 2850* (USM, US); Castrovirreyna Prov., 49 km SW of Huancavelica above Laguna Pultoc, 13°4'53.5"S, 75°2'57.9"W, 8 Mar 2002, *Peterson 16411 & Tovar* (US, USM); Castrovirreyna Prov., 4 km S of Choclococha and 8 km N of Santa Ines, 13°10'44"S, 75°5'15.3"W, 5 Apr 2004, *Peterson 18144 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Castrovirreyna Prov., 12 km S of Pucapampa at Abra Chonta, 13°4'53.2"S, 75°2'57.7"W, 4 Apr 2004, *Peterson 18134 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Castrovirreyna Prov., 3 km S of Pucapampa on road towards Abra Chonta, 13°3'6.5"S, 75°3'58.1"W, 4 Apr 2004, *Peterson 18130 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Castrovirreyna Prov., Abra Conota, E side of Hwy 3, 24 km N of Santa Ines and 57 km SSW of Huancavelica, 13°4'53"S, 75°2'58"W, 13 Mar 2007, *Peterson 20445*, *Soreng, Romaschenko & Susanibar Cruz* (US, USM); Huancavelica Prov., Nevado de Ajchi, 3 Aug 1961, *Tovar 3424* (USM, US); Huancavelica Prov., Cerro entre Huaytanayoco and Manta, 9 May 1956, *Tovar 2540* (USM, US); Huaytara Prov., N of new Hwy 24 from Pisco to Ayacucho, 124 air km E of Pisco and 21 air km E of San Antonio de Cusicancha, 13°28'47"S, 75°5'9"W, 12 Mar 2007, *Peterson 20417*, *Soreng, Romaschenko & Susanibar Cruz* (US, USM). **Junin.** Huaytapallana, Acopalca, 4 May 1961, *Tovar 3388* (US, USM); Junin Prov., Huampucocha, 8 May 1948, *Aguilar s.n.* (US); Yauli Prov., 134 km W of Lima on Hwy 20 towards La Oroya at Abra Anticonca, 5 Apr 1997, *Peterson 14032 & Tovar* (US, USM); Yauli Prov., above Morococha, 11 Jun 1940, *Asplund 11580* (US). **Lima.** Casapalca, 21 May 1922, *Macbride & Featherstone 851* (F, US); Canta Prov., 24 km E of Cullhuay on road towards Junin, 11°20'43.3"S, 76°26'14.1", 29 Mar 2004, *Peterson 18023 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM). **Moquegua.** 82 km W of Mazo Cruz on road towards Humajalso, 16°52'57.3"S, 70°26'51"W, 17 Apr 2004, *Peterson 18307 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM); Mariscal Nieto Prov., 2 km E of El Cruce on road towards Huayfire and Puno, 1 Mar 1999, *Peterson 14566*, *Refulio Rodriguez & Salvador Perez* (US, USM); Mariscal Nieto Prov., 45 km E of Torata on road towards El Cruce, 2 Feb 1999, *Peterson 14555*, *Refulio Rodriguez & Salvador Perez* (US, USM). **Pasco.** Pasco Prov., 6 km W of Santa Rosario at Abra Antajirca, 11°2'26.7"S, 76°31'43"W, 30 Mar 2004, *Peterson 18053 & Refulio Rodriguez* (US, USM). **Puno.** Cerro Ichuasi, Coccachara, SW of Llave, 25 Oct 1946, *Pearson & Pearson 66* (US); Coccachara, SW of Llave, 27 Nov 1946, *Pearson & Pearson 100* (US); El Callao Prov., 4 km W of San Jose Ancomarca on road towards Capaso, 9 Mar 1999, *Peterson 14710*, *Refulio Rodriguez & Salvador Perez* (US, USM); Carabaya Prov., Fauchinta, Allinccapac, 10 Apr 1948, *Vargas 7176* (US). **Tacna.** Tacna Provincia, 19 km W of Alto Peru on road towards Tacna, 14 Mar 1999, *Peterson 14782*, *Refulio Rodriguez & Salvador Perez* (US, USM); Tarata Prov., 5 km SW of Cano on road towards Yabroco, 17 Mar 1999, *Peterson 14827*, *Refulio Rodriguez & Salvador Perez* (US, USM); Tarata Prov., Laguna Calere, 3 km NE of Cano, 17 Mar 1999, *Peterson 14824*, *Refulio Rodriguez & Salvador Perez* (US, USM); Tarata Prov., Cordellera del Barroso, 26 Mar 1998, *Cano 8155*, *LaTorre, Córdova & Baldeviano* (US, USM); Tarata Prov., 20 km NE of Tarata, 28 Jan 1952, *Pearson & Pearson 52-60* (US).

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